

Case Report

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A patient reported to the Department office Public Health Dentistry with a chief complaint of missing upper and lower teeth since 5 months. Patient gives history of exfoliation of teeth due to trauma 5 months ago.

Patient undergone surgery of fracture of maxilla and mandible 5 months ago from Hospital, Udaipur.

Pre-operative Radiograph And Intra Oral Photograph

OPG Reveals- Two surgical miniplates evident which extends from right Para symphysis and symphysis to left Para symphysis and symphysis region. Missing tooth -11-14,21,22,32-42 Root Stumps -14,22,23.

□ **Treatment Plan:** Intentional RCT-33,34,43 and FPD-33-43
Flexible RPD -11-14,21,22,

Root Canal Procedure Done

Tooth Preparation Done -33,34,43

Fabrication of Maxillary Custom Tray & Border Moulding

Flexible Removable Partial Denture Fabricated

Post Operative Intraoral Photograph

Pre Op & Post Op Photograph of Patient